

Data set for Combined ITs and Sensors investigation under electromagnetic influences

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Test	Investigation of the ratio and phase displacement error variations caused by the influences of currents on the voltage transformer and of voltages on the current transformer in combined ITs and sensors						
Influence factor 1	Influences of currents on the voltage transformer						
Influence factor 2 (if combined with 1)	influences of voltages on the current transformer						
The measured parameters	Ratio error $\varepsilon_{i(u)}$ and phase displacement $\delta_{i(u)}$						
Combined ITs under test	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; text-align: center;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="background-color: #0056b3; color: white;">Lower U / Lower I</th> <th style="background-color: #0056b3; color: white;">Higher U / Higher I</th> <th style="background-color: #0056b3; color: white;">Higher U / Higher I</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td> ALCE Comb. IT RVD 22/√3 kV K: 10000, Cl:1 RC 1.6 kA : 0.15 V (0.18V@60Hz)						
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ALCE Comb. IT RVD 22/√3 kV K: 10000, Cl:1 RC 1.6 kA : 0.15 V (0.18V@60Hz)							
Measurement procedure (short description)	Several types of combined ITs and sensors have been tested to investigate the ratio and phase displacement error variations caused by the influences of currents on the voltage transformer/sensor and of voltages on the current transformer/sensor in combined ITs and sensors according to the methods given in Std. IEC 61869-4 [std] and the variations have been calculated by using formulas given in the related standard. To verify these calculated variations, a measurement setup consisting of two parts for the generation and measurement of the quantities was developed.						
Measurement Setup (short description)	<p>Two programmable power supplies and transformer based voltage and current amplifiers form the generation part while reference transformers and commercial test sets take place in the measurement part of the setup. The setup shown in Figure 1 has a typical measurement uncertainty of better than 20 ppm for both voltage and current ITs (100 ppm for sensors) with an adjustment of phase angle capability of 1 m° resolution.</p>						

Figure 1. Measurement setup for influence tests

Main results (tables, plots,...)

Remarkable greatest possible variations have been calculated during the tests of 22 kV/1.2 kA combined ITs and 22 kV/1.6 kA combined sensors (Table I).

Figure 2 shows the calculated and measured VT error variations of a combined IT. According to the angle between the current and the voltage phasors, the end points of error lie on circles round the points of the VT errors without current influence.

Figure 2. Influence of current transformer on voltage transformer for 22 kV/1.2 kA combined IT.

Similarly, voltage influences on the current sensor (Rogowski coil) of a combined sensor were measured for 5 % of its rated current. **And, the differences between the calculated and measured variations are found in a good agreement of below 0.01 %.**

Combined IT / Sensor	Calculated Variations		Measured Variations	
	in Voltage Error (%)	in Current Error (%)	in Voltage Error (%)	In Current Error (%)
22kV/1.2kA	± 0.321	± 0.022	± 0.325	± 0.023
22kV/1.6kA	± 0.070	± 5.20	± 0.072	± 5.21

Results show that the higher currents in combined ITs the higher influences on voltage errors. And, the higher voltages the higher influences on current sensor errors.

References

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Attached files

Name: Influence Test.xlsx

Description: The excel file contains 6 sheets. Name of the sheets and short explanation are given below.

ALCE_Combi_VT: influences of currents on the voltage transformer in ALCE Combined IT

ALCE_Combi_CT: influences of voltages on the current transformer in ALCE Combined IT

	<p>Esitaş_Combi_VT: influences of currents on the voltage transformer in ESİTAŞ Combined IT</p> <p>Esitaş_Combi_CT: influences of voltages on the current transformer in ESİTAŞ Combined IT</p> <p>ABB_Combi_Sensor_VT: influences of currents on the voltage transformer in ABB Combined Sensor</p> <p>ABB_Combi_Sensor_CT: influences of voltages on the current transformer in ABB Combined Sensor</p>
<p>Agree to make the data public ? (yes/no)</p>	<p>yes</p>